

THE ROLE OF THE INNOVATION MECHANISM IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE AGRICULTURAL SECTOR

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ABSTRACT

One of the main directions of the economic policy of the Azerbaijani government in the modern era is to accelerate the innovative economy, apply the most advanced technologies in our country in line with the modernization strategy, and, as a result, implement regionally scaled programs. The article discusses the process of changes in the growth dynamics of the agricultural sector in our republic, the positive results of flexible decisions adopted during the independence period, and the integration of the latest examples of world practice and advanced innovations in harmony with rapid development into the acceleration of agricultural sector growth.

Keywords: Innovative economy, advanced technology, productivity, structure of agricultural lands, arable lands.

INTRODUCTION. As a result of agricultural reforms carried out in Azerbaijan, significant potential opportunities have emerged for increasing agricultural production and improving productivity. The application of new technologies in the agricultural sector and the conduction of scientific and innovative research have become pressing issues today. Within the research framework, the impact of the application of scientific-technical ideas and research on increasing aggregate income in the agricultural sector is quantitatively assessed using modern mathematical models that characterize the most innovative economic development. Consequently, the economic security of any country directly depends on the sustainable development of agriculture. In today's era of rapid population growth and intensifying global climate change, the necessity for states to have an efficiently functioning agricultural sector is becoming more apparent. An efficient agricultural sector implies achieving higher agricultural production with fewer resource expenditures. In this sense, international experience shows that differences in agricultural productivity in countries with similar natural and economic conditions reflect the effectiveness of their agricultural policies (1).

The agricultural sector, as a crucial sphere of the Azerbaijani economy, constitutes approximately 5-6% of GDP and about 37-40% of employment. At least two-thirds of the population's consumption fund is directly provided by this sector. Ongoing research has shown that under the influence of innovative scientific and technological advancements in agriculture, cost minimization and income maximization issues are being resolved (2).

The development of the agricultural sector and ensuring food security are among the main directions highlighted in the "Azerbaijan-2020: Vision for the Future" Development Concept. When assessing the role of the agricultural sector in the national economy, the necessity of the reforms undertaken in this sector be-

comes evident. The agricultural sector serves as the primary source of raw materials for industrial enterprises, meets a significant part of the essential consumption needs of the population, provides employment for a large portion of the workforce in labor-intensive production countries, increases domestic demand for various industrial products, contributes to foreign currency inflows due to exports, and, most importantly, guarantees the country's food and economic security (5).

The full depiction of Azerbaijan's agricultural reform period can be outlined as follows: economic growth (reflected in GDP), the dynamics of economic growth over the past decade, the share of the agricultural sector in this dynamic, the separate dynamics of the agricultural sector over the last decade, the theory and methodology of innovation-based economic growth and its further development, and the share of the agricultural sector in innovation-based economic growth (6).

A legal, socio-economic framework has been established to ensure the dynamic development of the agricultural sector. The activities of local farmers, agricultural production cooperatives, and family farms have opened up extensive opportunities for the efficient use of available natural and economic potential. The foundation of modern economic and social development lies in the activation of innovation activities and the widespread dissemination of innovative technologies, products, and services. Currently, about 70% of global GDP growth is attributed to the emergence and management of innovation technologies (4). Additionally, specific methods and models should be used to describe the regularities and characteristics of innovation activity.

Azerbaijan's agricultural sector has enormous potential. Successfully implemented land reforms and other related factors have created extensive opportunities for the further development of the private sector in agriculture (3). Initial analyses have shown that inno-

vation activities in agriculture yield the following benefits: economic, social, ecological, technical, technological, commercial, and budgetary. These benefits, in turn, foster intensive growth in the agricultural sector.

EXTENSIVE AND INTENSIVE METHODS OF DEVELOPMENT. It is essential to note that there are two types of development: extensive and intensive. In extensive development, production means are proportionate to labor force growth, whereas in intensive development, the rate of labor force growth surpasses the rate of increase in production means. Thus, the economic development rate of the agricultural sector consists of two components. The application of new technologies and the results of scientific and innovative research influence the intensive growth rate in agriculture. Innovations encompass new scientific and technical ideas, new products, new technologies, new production processes, and the opening of new markets. Innovations have the potential to disrupt the equilibrium of the existing system of prices, costs, and revenues. As a result, unprofitable product circulation ceases, and an innovation mechanism that continuously supports market processes is stimulated.

The "innovation economy" (knowledge economy, intellectual economy) is a type of economy based on the continuous flow of innovation, constant technological improvement, and the production and export of high-value-added, high-tech products and technologies. Effective productivity, biological productivity, and even yield per hectare decrease due to plant diseases or pests. By multiplying the effective yield per hectare by the cultivated area, we determine total productivity. Total output multiplied by the additional product value gives the revenue, which, in turn, reflects the agricultural (food processing) production or total added value (7).

In recent years, one of the main directions of the European Union's agricultural policy has been the ecological adaptation of agriculture. This is related to the increasing demand for environmentally friendly food products grown without mineral fertilizers and pesticides. For example, in the United Kingdom, such products constitute one-fourth of total demand. One of the main components of the scientific strategy ensuring innovation-based agro-economic growth in Azerbaijan is the application of new efficient agricultural technologies in crop production to increase yield and quality. Among these research areas, greater utilization of genetically pure (or genetically improved) varieties to increase their share in total production plays a crucial role in ensuring quality product production and food security.

PROBLEMS IN EXPANDING AGRICULTURAL BIODIVERSITY THROUGH INNOVATIVE METHODS. The study employs methods of evaluating the varieties, hybrids, and forms of selected agricultural biodiversity and consolidating the results into databases for analysis. Conducting large-scale research to ensure the production of high-quality, durable, and environmentally friendly agricultural products is essential, as is the application of information technology and modern innovative selection methods in these studies (8).

One of the critical factors influencing crop productivity in agriculture is the proper selection of arable land, efficient use of irrigation water, impact of water stress, adjustment of organic and mineral fertilizer application to standards, and soil quality assessment. If these requirements are not met or properly integrated, agricultural production will decline.

Nearly 40% of irrigated lands in the republic suffer from erosion, while 57.7% are affected by salinization, desertification, and other forms of land degradation. Given the limited arable land (0.195 ha per person) and agricultural land (0.53 ha per person), and the importance of food security, agricultural lands should be used more efficiently and restricted from conversion to other purposes. Efforts should focus on preventing desertification, erosion, and salinization while rehabilitating degraded lands.

To ensure the sustainable development of agriculture, major priority directions should be determined, along with increasing the cultivation and production of priority crops. Research methods and models investigated for high-quality and eco-friendly agricultural production play a significant role in the agricultural sector, and the application of information technologies and modern statistical selection methods is of great importance.

To establish a system ensuring the production of high-quality, durable, and environmentally friendly agricultural products, the research methods and models investigated play a significant role in achieving high-yield and eco-friendly production in the agricultural sector. The application of information technologies and modern innovative selection statistical methods in these studies is of great importance. Based on the findings of the conducted research, the following actions are considered appropriate:

- Prioritizing efficient, innovative methods in the cultivation of essential food crops included in the necessary consumption basket (wheat, barley, potatoes, onions, tomatoes, cucumbers, eggplants, peppers) to enhance the quality and productivity indicators of these plants;
- Restoring soil fertility, which plays a crucial role in increasing crop yields, and, in some cases, improving soil fertility indicators to achieve higher results when calculating the full economic profitability coefficients of soil productivity;
- Considering methodological requirements in refining agricultural sector observations, including economic accounting, labor costs in the agricultural sector, rural population structure, workforce, migration of rural residents, and the use of various data sources;
- Utilizing sources such as agricultural censuses, economic surveys in agriculture, population censuses, demographic observations, labor force and household surveys, and other databases to compile agricultural statistical data;
- Collecting necessary statistical data (social, demographic, economic, etc.) for assessing research conducted in rural development statistics.

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